

Using a Stacking Classifier to Predict Outcomes of Squat Mechanics

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Abstract:

When performing a squat, it is important to maintain proper form. If improper form is maintained while squatting, it could be detrimental to the squatter and lead to severe, debilitating injuries or long-term joint damage. To assist in proper form maintenance, a supervisor is usually required. However, in some places, professional supervision is not available, and improper form cannot be corrected. This model aims to aid in that problem by providing an analysis of the user's squat. By doing so, it offers an accessible tool for squat form assessment.

The model was trained using previously labeled squat data. By using biomechanical features, such as knee angles, hip angles, leaning angles, and symmetry, the model evaluates the squat as an integer from zero to five. These values directly correspond to feedback: correct, shallow, forward lean, knees caving in, heels off ground, and asymmetric squat.

Multiple different models were considered when coding the final model. These models were LogisticRegression, AdaBoost, Random Forest, GradientBoosting, XGBoost, LightGBM, and StackingClassifier. When evaluating the final model, two constraints had to be employed: high accuracy for consistency, and low time for convenience. After employing these two constraints, the final product ended up being a StackingClassifier using XGBoost and LGBMClassifier, with LogisticRegression as the meta classifier.

The Knee Biomechanics Model ended up achieving a 95.795% test accuracy after fine tuning, v. It took one to two minutes to train the model, meaning it was relatively convenient. It had high values for precision, recall, and F1-Score across all the classes. These results display that machine learning can effectively classify squat mechanics and provide reliable feedback on the identification of squat deviation.

Purpose:

The purpose of this project is to analyze squat forms and give an objective, unbiased grading based on six provided metrics. By using past entries and grades, the model was taught to analyze specific angles and grade the squat based on them. The reason it was created is to provide a professional-grade analysis for squatting when it may not be available. Places like rehab centers and high schools depend on squats as a means for strength development, and sometimes, there may not be enough resources to ensure the squat is done correctly. This could lead to severe, debilitating injuries or long-term joint damage. The knee biomechanics model aims to mitigate this risk by providing an objective metric to correct squat form, which allows people a safe and convenient way to grade their squat to support safe squatting and enhance strength and recovery. It predicts the outcomes based on six classes, where each class corresponds to an integer between 0 and 5: zero is a correct squat, one is a shallow squat, two is a forward lean, three means knees caving in, four means heels off the ground, and five means asymmetric squat. By providing one of these six values, the squat biomechanics model successfully gives an accurate interpretation of the squat.

Code Breakdown:

To make this project, the tools were imported to utilize a variety of functions. Next, information was loaded so that the model could learn. After that, the information and outcome were separated to properly teach the model. After that, a training and testing set was made by splitting the original set to make sure the model understood the information. Then, a learning method was implemented which trained on the data to predict outcomes. After that, the data was learned, and the model was tested. Finally, a graph was made comparing different learning methods and the accuracy of the outcomes.

First, the libraries were imported that made this possible. These include *pandas*, *math*, *kagglehub*, *train_test_split*, *accuracy_score*, *classification_report*, *mean_squared_error*, *os*, *StandardScaler*, and *matplotlib.pyplot*. In addition, the learning methods, or the classifiers, were imported. This model uses *LGBMClassifier*, *XGBClassifier*, *LogisticRegression*, and *StackingClassifier*; however, importing additional classifiers is recommended for experimentation.

After all the libraries have been loaded, the data was loaded and processed. After finding the needed file, the path was copied and placed into the code. However, the path was incomplete and led to a folder. By using the *os* library to connect the folder to the file, the file was extracted and processed. Once done, the X- and y-values were set by taking the entire file and dropping or keeping specific columns. For example, the y-value was the outcome of the squat, ranging from zero to five, while the x-values were all of the angles. After that, the data was split into a train-test split by using the *train_test_split* function, with the *random_state* being 42 and the split being 80%-20%.

Once the data was loaded, the processing model was made. Although the project only used *LogisticRegression*, *XGBClassifier*, *StackingClassifier*, and *LGBMClassifier*, the model was also tested using *RandomForestClassifier*, *GradientBoostingClassifier*, *AdaBoostClassifier*, *HistGradientBoostingClassifier*, and *DecisionTreeClassifier*. A variable called *model* was created and a classifier was used to define it. For example, if using a *LogisticRegression* model for training, the code written would be *model = LogisticRegression()*. After defining the model, hyperparameters were inserted inside to refine it. This project had multiple different models with different hyperparameters to optimize performance.

After defining the model, the `model.fit()` function was used to make the model learn the training data. Once the model learned the data, a variable was made to be the predicted y-values and the function `model.predict()` was used to predict y-values based on `X_test`. This tested the model based on what it had learned. To determine the accuracy values, the `accuracy_score` and `classification_report` sub libraries were used. Using this accuracy value, the model was constantly iterated until the final desired accuracy was acquired.

Finally, using the `matplotlib.pyplot` library, a graph was made comparing different models' training and testing accuracy based on their accuracy values. This shows which models performed best and which models performed worse, offering a visual interpretation of the metrics in the project.

Values:

Basic information regarding the model is provided. This includes the train-test split, values included, numerical values, final accuracy, final RMSE, and

Values	Number
Train-Test Split	80% - 20%
Total Train Values	37953
Total Test Values	9489

Total Values	47442
Value Names	left_knee_angle, right_knee_angle, left_hip_angle, right_hip_angle, left_ankle_angle, right_ankle_angle, spine_angle, torso_lean, left_knee_lateral, right_knee_lateral, symmetry_score, hip_depth
Final Train Accuracy	99.68645429873791%
Final Test Accuracy	95.79513120455264%
Final RMSE	0.809757128805276

The train and test values of the models have been plotted below, arranged from least accurate testing to most accurate testing. First comes AdaBoost, then LogisticRegression, then the optimized AdaBoost, RandomForestClassifier, and HistGradientBoostingClassifier. After that is XGBoost, GradientBoostingClassifier, and LGBMClassifier. Finally, with the highest testing accuracy and serving as the current model for the program, is the StackingClassifier.

The table below is a direct copy of the classification metric, provided to help analyze the efficiency of the model. Precision means how many times it guessed the right outcome out of the total guesses of that outcome. Recall means how many out of a particular outcome it guessed right. The F1-Score gives a value balancing the precision and recall to describe how well the class is doing. Finally, the support gives the number of models tested in the test dataset.

Class	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
0	0.91	0.97	0.94	1546
1	0.96	0.96	0.96	1553

2	0.98	0.97	0.97	1576
3	0.99	0.98	0.99	1538
4	0.99	0.98	0.98	1676
5	0.92	0.89	0.90	1600

The table below serves as a listing for all of the testing and training values, along with their margins of difference. This table is arranged as the first model used to the last model used.

Model	Train Accuracy	Test Accuracy	Margin
Logistic Regression	50.381%	50.669%	-0.288%
RandomForestClassifier	100%	88.629%	11.371%
GradientBoostingClassifier	99.368%	94.320%	5.048%
XGBClassifier	98.343%	94.299%	4.044%
AdaBoostClassifier (Basic)	45.211%	46.169%	-0.958%
AdaBoostClassifier (Advanced)	75.480%	73.169%	2.311%

HistGradientBoostingClassifier	98.121%	94.204%	3.917%
LGBMClassifier	99.513%	95.331%	4.182%
StackingClassifier (LGBM + XGB)	99.686%	95.795%	3.891%

Observations:

When coding this model, several observations were made that contributed to its creation. To start, when coding the program, the library *StandardScaler* was ineffective at improving the performance of the model. In fact, it negatively impacted the values, as *StandardScaler* widened the train-test gap, increasing overfitting while simultaneously lowering test accuracy. This is because all of the classifiers besides Logistic Regression were tree-based classifiers. Instead of relying on the magnitude of the data to perform tests, tree-based classifiers check orders of values to make changes. If one value in the table is larger than another value in the table, it makes a rule to analyze and predict outcomes. *StandardScaler* changes these values, increasing their complexity. As a result, these tree-based classifiers have to make their predictions more advanced. When the classifications become too advanced, the model punishes the classifier, forcing it to change values. This constant changing can lead to overfitting or underfitting. *StandardScaler*'s changing the values led to an increase in overfitting in the model, resulting in poorer performance.

Another observation made was the recall on class five being consistently lower than the recall for other classes. When printing the classification report, the model was consistently scoring below 80% for the recall on class 5 for single classifiers. This meant that all single

classifiers were incapable of achieving a high recall accuracy for class 5. When analyzing the values of class 5, the features were significantly similar to the values of the other classes. This confused the model and led it to predicting true class 5 values as classes 0-4. To fix this problem, various methods were utilized; however, no method was strong enough to increase the recall of class 5 without decreasing the recall and accuracy of other values. In the end, the measure taken to increase class 5's accuracy was adding weights and setting class 5's weight to 1.3, which was slightly larger than the other classes' values at 1.0. This increased weight meant that in times of doubt, the model will lean more towards class 5 than the other classes.

While testing the different classifiers, it was evident that time was a significant constraint that influenced the decision of the final model. While testing GradientBoostingClassifier, the training time was 17 minutes, which is excessively time consuming for a model to train and learn the data. In contrast, the Logistic Regression model took two seconds to analyze and fit to the data. This is because of the difference in training methods. Logistic Regression is a method of training that uses linear classification to separate data. This makes fitting a line to the data very simple. On the other hand, GradientBoostingClassifier uses an algorithm that runs the data multiple times, and it trains in a line, only running through the data again after running through it completely and analyzing loss. This meant that without completing one run, it could not start another, significantly increasing time to train. The tree-based models, on average, took over a minute to train to the data, which is a substantial amount of time.

Several observations were also made regarding the hyperparameters. When using the GradientBoostingClassifier and XGBClassifier, there was minimal accuracy change when altering the `min_samples_leaf` value for GradientBoostingClassifier, and the same change was present for `min_split_loss` for XGBClassifier. The `min_samples_leaf` was changed from three to

six, but yielded minimal results, and the `min_split_loss` was changed from 0.2 to 0.5, and gave a worse accuracy score, lowering the accuracy by about 0.9%. In contrast, increasing the `max_depth` had a much more significant impact on the accuracy of the model, and within a certain range, boosted the performance. If the range of `max_depth` is between 6 and 8, the model performed optimally. However, values under 6 caused underfitting and values above 8 caused overfitting. When using XGBoost, a significant problem arose: the recall for class 5 was 78%, which, although the highest out of all the singular models, was inadequate. To fix this problem, *numpy*, *SMOTE*, and *SMOTETomek* were utilized. When using the *numpy* library, the function `numpy.where()` was implemented to give class 5 extra weight. This meant the model would lean towards class 5 when in doubt of the value. The library *SMOTE* creates artificial data points based on discrepancies between values in a chart. It enhances those discrepancies so a model is better trained to analyze those differences. The third library, *SMOTETomek*, is a library that splits data whose data points are clustered too close together. Even after attempting to use all three techniques, none were helpful in increasing the recall of class 5 without harming the values of the other classes.

Finally, there were observations made according to trends in the data. If the model did not perform very poorly, it would possess varying degrees of overfitting. The following accuracy values are drawn from testing results. Logistic Regression, the base Adaptive Booster, and the optimized Adaptive Booster gave testing accuracies of about 51%, 46%, and 73%, respectively. These three models performed sub-optimally and also had no overfitting. The gap for Logistic Regression was -0.3%; the gap for the base AdaBoost was -0.9%; and the gap for the optimized AdaBoost was 2.3%. These values were calculated by subtracting the training accuracy from the testing accuracy. The gap between the training and testing accuracy is very low, as seen by the

performance metrics, proving the accuracy is poor but the transferability is great. Conversely, the models which performed well had high performance, but relatively poor transferability. The most effective model, a StackingClassifier combining the optimized LGBMClassifier and the XGBClassifier, gave a 95.80% testing accuracy; however, it had a 3.9% gap between the training and testing accuracies, which points to slight overfitting. Likewise, the LGBMClassifier had an accuracy of 95.33, but had an overfitting value of about 4.2%. The XGBClassifier had similar results, with a 94.29% accuracy but a 4% margin. HistGradientBoostingClassifier gave a test accuracy of 94.20, with a difference of 3.9%. The GradientBoostingClassifier gave an accuracy of 94.32% with an overfitting gap of 4.1%. The most pronounced overfitting instance was with RandomForestClassifier, exhibiting an accuracy of 88.63% but a generalization gap of almost 11.4%. Although most of these discrepancies across training and testing data are relatively low compared to their accuracies, the values are still undeniable and point to slight overfitting whenever the model performs well.

Coding Process:

First, Logistic Regression was used to code the program. However, it performed poorly, only giving a 50.67% training accuracy. Next, the model was switched to RandomForestClassifier, which once the hyperparameters were optimized, gave a test accuracy score of 88.63%. Although this was good, the train accuracy score was 100%, pointing to overfitting in the model, which was undesirable. The model was switched to GradientBoostingClassifier, which gave it a 94.32% test accuracy and a 99.37% training accuracy. Although these numbers indicate slight overfitting, it was not a big problem as the model was still able to perform well. However, there was a significant problem in the amount of time it took for the model to accurately train, taking about 17 minutes. This led to the model

being switched to XGBoost. This model, although it reduced the testing accuracy by about 0.03%, significantly reduced the time taken to fit the model to the data. In addition, it also provided less overfitting, which meant the model was more generalizable. However, the issue with this model was that it displayed only a 78% recall for class 5, which, although better than all the other models' recalls for class 5, was still not great. This led to the implementation of the *numpy* library, to use the `numpy.where()` function to make the model more biased towards class five. However, this made minimal impact to class 5 while also negatively impacting class 0's performance, which corresponds to a correct squat. Next, the *SMOTE* library was applied to create artificial data points to the dataset to amplify the differences in classes 0-4 and class 5. However, while this did have a good impact on class 5, it negatively impacted class 0, similar to the *numpy* library. Finally, to eliminate this confusion, *SMOTETomek* was tested. By simultaneously creating new values and emphasizing the differences, this model attempted to change the values for the dataset since they were clustered too close together. However, when utilizing it, it had almost no effect on the performance of the model, yielding no meaningful results. Next, the model was switched to `HistGradientBoostingClassifier`, which provided slightly worse metrics, so the model was changed again into `LightGradientBoostingMachineClassifier`, which provided the best metrics with a 95.33% testing accuracy. However, the recall for class 5 was still low, so the model was changed again. The final iteration used a `StackingClassifier` with the base estimators being the two most ideal choices, XGBoost and `LGBMClassifier`. The final estimator was `LogisticRegression`, and once the model was implemented and utilized, it returned the highest testing accuracy of 95.80%. This model became the final model used for the project.

Conclusion:

The Knee Biomechanics model aims to provide a consistent, objective grading metric for everybody performing squats. By using a StackingClassifier to combine two strong ML models, this project successfully provided an accurate benchmark to analyze squat performance.

Many lessons were learned through coding this model, most notably the understanding of the use of different classification models and their individual purposes, abilities, and constraints. Another lesson is an improved understanding of both ML model development and the biomechanics of squatting.

One concern regarding the code is the 4.205% error rate in performance. This model performs at roughly 95.795% testing accuracy, meaning there will be some mistakes. In addition, the model may take a significant amount of time to load the data, which would be inconvenient for the user.

Future improvements could be made to enhance the accuracy of the model and the time taken to train it. To start, the model should be further fine-tuned in order to maximize the accuracy from the models. In addition, a computer vision pipeline should be added to improve the usage of the model, so that a video can be added for direct analysis. Finally, instead of printing out accuracy, the model should provide the analysis for the squat based on the outcome with full sentences.

Project Location:

To maximize the accessibility of the model, it has been uploaded to Github. The project file can be accessed as an .ipynb file ready to download from this link:

https://github.com/AvishBansal1/aiml/blob/main/Knee_Biomechanics_Model.ipynb

Works Cited

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